

MOTHER TONGUE INTERFERENCE: ITS EFFECT TO THE ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION SKILLS OF BA ELS STUDENTS IN A UNIVERSITY IN SULU, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of mother tongue interference on the English pronunciation skills of the BA ELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. Specifically, this study dealt with the following objectives: (1) to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age and year level; (2) to identify the level of English pronunciation skills of selected BA ELS students of MSU-Sulu; (3) to identify the effect of mother tongue interference to the English pronunciation skills of the said students; and (4) to ascertain if there is a significant difference on the level of students' English pronunciation skills when the data are grouped according to the profile. Descriptive research survey was used in this study. This study focused only on the BA ELS students who were officially enrolled during school year 2022-2023. Forty respondents were selected using stratified random sampling. The researchers used self-developed questionnaire as the instrument of this study. Frequency, percentage, weighted arithmetic mean, t-test for independent samples and one-way analysis of variance were the statistical tools used in this study to answer the stated research questions. The findings revealed that the level of English pronunciation skills of the students is very satisfactory. In addition, the respondents agreed that mother tongue interference has negative effects on their English pronunciation skills. Furthermore, it revealed that there is no significant difference in level of English pronunciation skills of the students when the data are

grouped according to the profile. In view of the findings, the researchers suggested that teachers may monitor the pronunciation skills of the students especially during class hour, and may look for teaching methods and instructional strategies that can motivate the students to frequently speak in English. Finally, the school administration may create measures for improvement of the speaking ability of the BA ELS students.

Keywords: *Mother tongue interference, English pronunciation skills, Sulu, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The concept of Mother tongue is a traditional term for a person's native language meaning, a language learned from birth. Mother tongue most often was called a first language, dominant language, home language, and native tongue and so on. Contemporary linguists and educators commonly use the term "L1" to refer to a first or native language (the mother tongue), and the term L2 to refer to a second language or a foreign language that is being studied (Nordquist, 2019). One of the main problems of mother tongue interference is that it can impede communication between people. For example, if someone is speaking their native language and another person is speaking a different language, it can be difficult to understand each other. Another problem is that it can limit a person's ability to learn a new language. If someone is constantly speaking their native language, they may not have the opportunity to practice and learn a new language. The term interference, on the other hand, according to Weinreich (2011) as cited by Nishanthi, R. (2020), is defined as a situation when the person (bilingual) uses norm or rule from their first languages involved to their second languages as a result of the language contact on both languages. Interference is the deviation of language norm in usage as the effect of multilingual toward some other languages.

The problem on mother tongue interference was demonstrated by many studies. Denizer (2017) noted that in English language, the most challenging part is grammar, while the most difficult and influenced skills is speaking. He also claimed that participants had difficulty speaking without any preparation. Denizer (2017) finally added that the results of his study indicated that mother tongue interferes in almost all aspects. In addition, the data obtained from the study of Fitriani and Julkarnain (2019) showed that the learning process of the target language was affected by the first language.

Based on the researchers' initial review of literature, it was found out that there is a limited study on this topic especially in most academic institutions in the Southern Philippines. In Mindanao State University-Sulu, for example, students who used English as a medium of communication tend to mix it with their mother tongue. This is true to most college students regardless of gender, age and year level.

The researchers also believed that people should take into consideration the possible interference of mother tongue in their pronunciation skills. So, the main goal of this study was to determine the effect of mother tongue interference on the students' pronunciation skills in English. It also aimed to determine the effective ways for

overcoming mother tongue interference. Finally, this study will be beneficial to the students, teachers, curriculum planners and other stakeholders of an academic institution.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effect of mother tongue interference to the English pronunciation skills of selected BA ELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research inquiries:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age and year level?
2. What is the level of English pronunciation skills of selected BA ELS students of MSU-Sulu?
3. What is the effect of mother tongue interference to the English pronunciation skills of the said students?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of students' English pronunciation skills when the data are grouped according to profile?

METHODOLOGY

In this section, the research methodology is presented. It contains the research design, locale of the study, research sampling, research respondents, research instrument, validation of research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This research study employed a quantitative method to obtain information about the effect of mother tongue interference to the English pronunciation skills of selected BA ELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. To be specific, the researchers used descriptive survey design. This study employed a descriptive method of research, with primary data gathered through individual unstructured interviews (Ancho & Park, 2023).

Locale of the Study

This research study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu particularly at the College of Arts and Sciences. The said college is adjacent to the Academic Building. It is beside the Student Center and behind the Integrated Science Laboratory Building.

Sampling Technique

The researchers used stratified random sampling for the selection of the respondents. Stratified random sampling is a sampling which involve chosen some group of items from population based on classification and random selection. It involves separating the target population element in to homogenous, mutually exclusive segment, from each segment simple random sampling is chosen. The selected sample from different strata is combined to have a single sample. Stratified sampling is the technique of probability sampling in which the characteristics of a precise variable are interpreted in the universe relative to this variable (Iliyasu & Etikan, 2021).

Respondents of the Study

Forty out of 264 BA ELS students who were officially enrolled during the school year 2022-2023 served as respondents of this study. They were asked to answer the survey questionnaire prepared by the researchers.

Research Instrument

The instrument used by researchers in this study for acquiring primary data was a survey questionnaire which contained three parts. The first part is about the personal data of the respondents which contains their name, gender, age, and year level. The second part, on the other hand, contains items about the effects of mother tongue interference to the English pronunciation skills of the students. The researchers used the following 4-point rating scale as response choices in the second part of the questionnaire: strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. Lastly, the third part contains ten words that were used to determine the level of pronunciation skills of the students.

Validation of Research Instrument

The researchers first submitted the survey questionnaire to their thesis adviser for possible corrections and suggestions. After having been checked by the adviser, the researchers proceeded to at least three experts in research specifically from the faculty of the College of Arts and Sciences for the validation of the research instrument.

Data Gathering Procedure

The first thing that the researchers did was to write a letter to Prof. Ajid M. Sari, the dean of the College of Arts and Sciences, to allow them to conduct their research study on the said college. Afterwards, the researchers sent another letter to the chairman of the Department of Languages, for the gathering of data and for the launching of the questionnaire on April 3, 2023.

Statistical Treatment of Data

For the statistical treatment of data, the researchers used frequency and percentage to identify the profile of the respondents. In addition, the researchers used mean to determine the level of English pronunciation skills of selected BA ELS students and the effect of mother tongue interference on the students' said skills. The researchers also used t-test for independent samples and one-way analysis of variance to ascertain if there is a significant difference in the level of the students' English pronunciation skills according to their profile.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered from 40 respondents. The tables are presented according to the order of the research questions in the statement of the problem.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	15	37.5%
Female	25	62.5%
Total	40	100%

Table 1.1. shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. As shown in the table, 15 or 37.5% of the respondents are males, while there are 25 or 62.5% of the respondents are females. This means that majority of the respondents of this study are females.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
19-23 years old	30	75.0%
24 years old and above	10	25.0%
Total	40	100%

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. As shown in the table, 30 or 75.0% of the respondents are 19-23 years old; while only 10 or 25.0% of the respondents are 24 years old and above. This implies that majority of the respondents of this study belong to the age bracket group of 19-23 years old.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level

Year Level	Frequency	Percent
1st Year	10	25.0%
2nd Year	10	25.0%
3rd Year	10	25.0%
4th Year	10	25.0%
Total	40	100%

Table 1.3 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of year level. As shown in the table, 10 or 25.0% of the respondents are in 1st year level, 10 or 25.0% of the respondents are in 2nd year level, 10 or 25.0% of the respondents are in 3rd year level and 10 or 25.0% of the respondents are in 4th year level. This implies that the distribution of the respondents of this study is equal across all year level.

Table 2 Level of English Pronunciation Skills of the Students

	Mean	SD	Description
Level of Pronunciation Skills	9.88	2.70	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 1.00-3.80 = Not Satisfactory; 3.81-6.61= Fairly Satisfactory; 6.62-9.42 = Satisfactory; 9.43-12.23 = Very Satisfactory; 12.24-15.00 = Outstanding

Table 2 shows the level of English pronunciation skills of the students. As shown in the table, the mean level of English pronunciation skills of the students is 9.88 which is very satisfactory.

Table 3 Effects of Mother Tongue Interference on English Pronunciation Skills

Statements	Mean	Description
1. It's challenging for me to speak or talk because I always mispronounce the words that I set to use in a conversation.	2.90	Agree
2. I tend to mix the words I uttered with a Tausug word.	2.85	Agree
3. I find it hard to pronounce in English because I'm used to speak in mother tongue.	2.72	Agree
4. I usually commit errors in my pronunciation.	2.70	Agree
5. I cannot pronounce the proper stress of the syllable.	2.65	Agree
6. I find it hard to speak in straight English.	2.65	Agree
7. I find English language difficult to pronounce.	2.63	Agree
8. I tend to have a poor diction.	2.45	Disagree
9. I cannot pronounce the letters "b, f, l, p, r, s, u, v, and z" in the words properly.	2.30	Disagree
10. I cannot pronounce the words correctly.	2.05	Disagree
Grand Mean	2.59	Agree

Table 3 shows the perceived effects of mother tongue interference on the English pronunciation skills of the students. As shown in the table, the students *agreed* on the

following indicators: *It's challenging for me to speak or talk because I always mispronounce the words that I set to use in a conversation, I tend to mix the words I uttered with a Tausug word, I find it hard to pronounce in English because I'm used to speak in mother tongue, I usually commit errors in my pronunciation, I cannot pronounce the proper stress of the syllables, I find it hard to speak in straight English, and I find English language difficult to pronounce.*

In contrary, the respondents *disagreed* that. *I tend to have a poor diction, I cannot pronounce the letters "b, f, l, p, r, s, u, v, and z" in the words properly and I cannot pronounce the words correctly.*

The grand mean of 2.59 with a verbal description of *agree* implies that the respondents agreed that mother tongue interference has negative effects on their English pronunciation skills.

Table 4.1 Results of Significant Difference in the Level of Students' English Pronunciation Skills based on Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value
Male	15	10.47	2.32	1.076	38	.289
Female	25	9.52	2.89			

p-value of 0.05 and below are significant and above .05 are not significant

Table 4.1 shows the significant difference on the level of students' English pronunciation skills based on gender. The findings showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores between male ($M = 10.47$, $SD = 2.33$) and female ($M = 9.52$, $SD = 2.89$); $t(1.076)$, $p = .289$.

Table 4.2 Results of Significant Difference on the Level of Students' English Pronunciation Skills based on Age

Age	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value
19-23 years old	30	10.07	2.741	.774	38	.444
24 years old and above	10	9.30	2.627			

p-value of 0.05 and below are significant and above .05 are not significant

Table 4.4.2 shows the significant difference on the level of students' English pronunciation skills based on age. The findings showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores between 19-23 years old ($M = 10.7$, $SD = 2.74$) and 24 years old and above ($M = 9.30$, $SD = 2.63$); $t(.774)$, $p = .444$.

Table 4.3 Results of Significant Difference on the Level of Students' English Pronunciation Skills based on Year Level

Year Level	N	Mean	SD	F	df	p-value
1st Year	10	9.70	3.16	.662	3 & 36	.581
2nd Year	10	10.80	2.62			
3rd Year	10	9.10	2.38			
4th Year	10	9.90	2.73			

p-value of 0.05 and below are significant and above .05 are not significant

Table 4.3 shows the ANOVA on the perceived effects on the level of students' English pronunciation skills according to year level. As shown in the table, the p-value of .581 is greater than the alpha level of .05. This means that the null hypothesis is accepted. In other words, there is no significant difference in the perceived effects on the level of students' English pronunciation skills when the data are classified according to year level.

Conclusions

To study the complexity of language is a difficult task. Indeed, the English pronunciation skills of the students and how mother tongue can interfere with these skills can be evaluated both positively and negatively. The main goal of the current study was to explore the effect of English pronunciation skills among selected BA ELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu.

In the light of the findings, the study concluded that the level of English pronunciation skills of the BA ELS students is very satisfactory. This means that students were able to pronounce the words appropriately despite not being a native speaker of English. It also concluded that mother tongue interference has negative effects on their English pronunciation skills. This means that mother tongue tends to affect the students' utterances of English words. Moreover, it is also concluded that there is no significant difference on the level of students' English pronunciation skills based on gender, age and year level. This implies that their English pronunciation skills is not dependent on their profile.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following are recommended:

A. Research Agenda

1. Provide a copy of this research study to other schools for their reference.
2. There is a need to conduct a follow-up study to verify the result of this research work.
3. Teachers may monitor the pronunciation skills of the students especially during class hour.

4. Teachers may look for teaching methods and instructional strategies that can motivate the students to frequently speak in English.
5. There may be a similar study to be conducted on a wider scope and setting.

B. Research Policies

1. The school administration may create a policy to improve the speaking ability of the students.
2. The school administration may coordinate and partner with line agencies who are experts in the training of teachers.
3. The school administration may establish an auditorium to be used for public speaking activities.
4. The school administration may create measures for improvement of the speaking ability of the BA ELS students.
5. The school administration may create a reward system for the faculty members especially those who are language teachers.

C. Research Problems

1. Mother Tongue Interference: Its Association with the Communication Skills of the Students
2. Level of Pronunciation Skills of the Students and their Academic Performance
3. Exploring the Pronunciation Skills of the Public-School Students in Sulu
4. Effectiveness of Using Differentiated Strategies in Improving Students' Pronunciation Skills
5. Strategies to Overcome Mother Tongue Interference

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby declare that an informed consent was obtained from the respondents of the study. In addition, the researchers assure that the information gathered from respondents are kept confidential. Plagiarism was strictly observed

throughout the research process, and that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research purposes.

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